

ORGANIC SEMICONDUCTOR LASERS

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The field of easily processed organic semiconductor lasers (OSLs) is young at little more than a decade old and advancing rapidly. It provides exciting new challenges and opportunities for light-emitting materials beyond organic light-emitting diodes. There have been many important developments over the past few years. Laser and material design have advanced to reduce thresholds, enabling OSLs to be pumped by compact solid-state sources. Broad tunability and simple fabrication have been shown as well as short pulse generation and broad-band optical amplification. These advances draw on well-known general features of organic semiconductors for any application, such as simple processing and the scope for tuning properties, and have stimulated work that exploits these properties in new ways. For example, the simple processing has enabled a remarkable range of laser structures to be made in very simple ways, including simple nanoimprinting of wavelength-scale features. In addition, the scope for blending to tune properties has been used to reduce thresholds considerably. Some of the other advances draw on properties of the materials that are more specific to lasing, such as strong absorption and broad spectra, and use these properties in many ways. The strong absorption (and associated strong stimulated emission) enables extraordinarily compact lasers and optical amplifiers to be made.

The broad spectra enable not only tuneable lasers to be made but also femtosecond pulse generation and broadband optical amplification. As we look to the future, it is important to keep in mind that this progress has been made mainly using materials developed for organic light-emitting diodes, so new opportunities and further progress can be expected from developing materials specifically for laser applications. Promising future directions include exploiting the compatibility with polymer optical fiber and using the distinctive chemical properties of organic semiconductors for sensing. Beyond that, electrical pumping remains a major challenge. However, a key

recent breakthrough is the demonstration of direct optical pumping of polymer lasers by gallium nitride diode lasers. Such indirect electrical pumping gives many of the advantages of electrical pumping and paves the way for OSLs to become practical sources, initially for use in a range of spectroscopic applications.

The external quantum efficiency (η_{ext}) of OLEDs is based on four factors: (i) the ratio of electron and hole injection, transport, and recombination (v), (ii) exciton formation efficiency (η_r), (iii) internal electroluminescence quantum yield (ϕ_p), and (iv) light out-coupling efficiency (η_p) (Figure 1). Obtaining the highest possible luminescence efficiency requires bringing each of the four factors as close to 100% as possible. Here, v is a physical quantity containing the ratio of electron and hole injection and transport, as well as the probability of electron and hole recombination. ϕ_p can have a value near to 100% by using a material with a high internal luminescence quantum yield.

Figure 1. OLED luminescence processes (carrier injection, transport, recombination, exciton formation/decay, and light extraction) and their efficiencies. Figures in parentheses represent refractive indices.

Although η_r is generally low (25% when fluorescent materials are used), the use of phosphorescent materials can theoretically provide an η_r of 75 to 100%. If a device is formed on a common glass substrate, η_p is low at about 20%. Therefore, if fluorescent materials are used as luminescent molecules, η_{ext} is approx 5% at most,

but with the use of a triplet exciton as a luminescence transition process can provide a luminescence efficiency theoretically 3 or more times higher. In instances where the intersystem crossing (ISC) probability is about 100%, a luminescence efficiency approximately 4 times higher can be achieved.

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